

The Effect of Mathway on Undergraduate Mathematics Students' Performance and Perception in Calculus in Bayelsa State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of Mathway on Mathematics students' performance and perception in Calculus in Bayelsa State. The study adopted quasi-experimental and descriptive survey research designs with non-equivalent groups. Three research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study was 208 students, with a sample size of 118 students including 77 males and 41 through purposive sampling technique. The reliability coefficient of the Students' Performance Test on Calculus was established at 0.79 using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation, while Cronbach alpha was used to obtain 0.85 for the Students' Perception Questionnaire in Calculus. Data obtained from the instruments were analysed using mean and standard deviation. The result revealed that the mean gain of Mathway group ($M=35.37$) is higher than that of the lecture method ($M=23.32$). The effect size of 12.05 indicates that the students taught with Mathway application were favoured more than those taught with the lecture method. Furthermore, ANCOVA results shows that there was a significant difference between the posttest mean performance scores of students' in Mathway group and the lecture method. The result also revealed that there was no significant difference between male and female students' mean performance in calculus when using Mathway. And student's perceptions toward the learning of calculus using Mathway was generally positive. Among others, it was recommended that Lecturers employ Mathway application for teaching and learning to enhance the performance and perception of undergraduate Mathematics students.

Keywords: Mathway, students' performance, gender and Perception

INTRODUCTION

Calculus is a branch of Mathematics with a wide application in other areas such as statistics, analytical geometry, algebra and almost all disciplines, such as Physics, Engineering, Medicine, Economics, Chemistry Geography, Computer Science and information systems. It is an area of Mathematics perceived as the main source of failure among undergraduates because of its nature, which are abstract and complex ideas. Others are unengaging teaching methods, inadequate course design, ineffective study techniques, and the classroom

environment (Saha, Akhi, & Saha, 2024; Chand, Chaudhary, Prasad & Chand, 2021).

Mathematics learning tools such as Mathway, Geogebra, Photomath, Todomath, Microsoft Math and others help develop the student's academic achievement and enhances their understanding. Also, it saves their effort and time and helps reduce the gap between students by reducing individual differences. Students who used smart device applications performed better than those students who did not use them. Therefore, the introduction of smart devices in learning and teaching may help students raise their academic achievement levels, which in turn leads to the quality of provided education (Etcuban & Pantinople, 2018; Fabian, Topping & Barron, 2018; Hadjinor, Asotigue & Pandangamun, 2021; Mhlanga, 2018; George & Charles-Ogan, 2023). The use of smart devices and the features they contain in teaching students of different ages to impact them positively more than if they were taught using traditional methods. This is because smart devices provide interactive educational applications that attract and entice students to learn and are suitable for their different abilities. Also, the ease of interaction with this information makes students attracted to and accepts the educational process. This helps to improve students' performance and raise their academic achievement levels, which leads to the effectiveness of the teaching and learning processes (Altaf, 2019; Alyan & Al-Qasimiyah, 2019; Al-Zahrani, 2019; Demir & Akpinar, 2018; Kattayat, Josey & Asha, 2017; Klimova, 2019; Quispe, et al., 2018; Costley, 2014).

Cantonjos & Labo (2018) determined the effectiveness of math apps in improving the performance of the grade 11 students in probability and statistics at Bagahanglad National High School, San Jacinto District in the Division of Masbate-Province, school year 2019-2020. The descriptive method of research would utilize in this study. The respondents were 50 Grade 11 students who were currently taking probability and statistics subject. The study used quantitative method to describe the performance level of the grade 11 learners in Probability and Statistics subject along the four identified topics and evaluate the Math Apps being used the Data analysis, and a qualitative method was used to know the effectiveness of the Math Apps in improving the performance of Grade 11 in Probability and Statistics subject. Data were gathered through test administration and interview. A Researcher-made instrument test questions and interviews schedule were utilized as the main instruments of the study.

Barrientos (2021) examined the use of math apps and the performance of grade 8 students in

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Mathematics under new normal education is underpinned by the TPACK framework of Shulman's (1987,1986) in describing how teacher's understanding of educational technologies and PCK interact with one another to produce effective teaching with technology. Analysis revealed that the pedagogical design as well the features design of Math Apps resulted to a very great extent. The level of the students' performance in Mathematics resulted in a great improvement from Developing into Proficient and Advanced stages.

Undergraduate students, particularly those in STEM majors, struggle with Calculus due to its abstract nature, ineffective teaching methods, and low attitude towards learning, and consequently exhibit poor performance in the subject. This difficulty stems from Mathematical anxiety and fear of the subject matter delivery, but innovative and interactive technologies have become palliatives in promoting positive attitudes and performance in Calculus.

Statement of the Problem

The use of digital tools in educational settings has altered the conditions of learning across multiple disciplines. Specifically, in the discipline of mathematics, online resources such as Mathway have been developed as effective aids in improving students' grasp and application of complicated mathematical concepts. Calculus, recognized for its difficulty, is a basic course for many undergraduate programs and frequently shapes students' attitudes about mathematics as a whole. Mathway functions as a problem-solving aid, allowing students to practice and confirm their calculus solutions, potentially affecting their learning outcomes and self-efficacy. However, finding a reliable and successful approach for teaching Calculus remains a significant challenge. Therefore, this study aims to explore the efficiency of Mathway on Performance and Perception of year one undergraduate Mathematics students in Calculus.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the difference in the performance of year one undergraduate Mathematics students taught Calculus using Mathway application and Lecture method?
2. What is the gender difference in the post-test mean performance scores of year one undergraduate Mathematics students' taught Calculus using Mathway application?

3. What is the perception of year one undergraduate Mathematics students' towards Calculus when using Mathway application?

Hypotheses

The understated null hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 percent significance level.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of year one undergraduate Mathematics students' taught Calculus using Mathway application and those taught using the Lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference between the post-test mean performance scores of male and female year one undergraduate Mathematics students who were taught Calculus using Mathway application.

Methodology

The population of the study comprised all 208 2022/2023 academic session students of Mathematics departments of five (5) National Universities Commission approved universities in Bayelsa State. The sample of this study includes 118 first-year undergraduate Mathematics students comprising 77 males representing 65.3% and 41 females representing 34.7% from two intact classes by purposive sampling. The instruments were: Students' Performance Test on Calculus (SPTC) and Students' Perception Questionnaire on Calculus (SPQC). The reliability coefficient for SPTC was determined using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient and a value of 0.79 was obtained. While a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was determined for SPQC using Cronbach's Alpha test. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of mean and standard.

Results and Discussion

Research question 1: What is the difference in the mean performance scores of year one undergraduate Mathematics students taught Calculus using Mathway application and Lecture method?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on performance of students in Calculus using Mathway application and lecture method

Group	n	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain	Effect Size
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Mathway	65	33.94	7.64	69.31	6.56	35.37	12.05
LM	53	32.57	7.53	55.89	8.26	23.32	

Results from table 1 shows a pre-test mean score of 33.94 with a standard deviation of 7.64 and a corresponding post-test mean of 69.31 with a standard deviation of 6.56 resulting into a mean gain of 35.37 for students that used Mathway for learning Calculus while a pre-test mean of 32.57 with a standard deviation of 7.53 and a post-test mean of 55.89 with a standard deviation of 8.26 and a corresponding mean gain of 23.32 was recorded for the group that used lecture method for learning Calculus. The result revealed that the mean gain of Mathway group (M=35.37) is higher than that of the lecture method (M=23.32). The effect size of 12.05 indicates that the students taught with Mathway were favoured more than those taught with the lecture method.

Research question two: What is the gender difference in the mean performance scores between year one undergraduate Mathematics students’ taught Calculus using Mathway application and the lecture method?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on performance Scores of male and female year one undergraduate Mathematics students in Calculus using Mathway application and the lecture method

Group	Gender	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Mathway	Male	33.71	7.11	69.39	6.36	35.68
	Female	34.33	9.62	69.17	7.03	34.84
Lecture Method	Male	32.89	7.87	57.25	7.10	24.36
	Female	31.88	6.95	53.00	9.92	21.12

From table 2 above, Mathway group had the highest mean gain for both male and female students, followed by the Lecture Method group. The results revealed that male students using the Mathway application had a mean gain of 35.68, while female students had a mean gain of 34.84. Male students using the Lecture Method had the lowest mean gain of 24.36,

while female students had a mean gain of 21.12. The Mathway application seemed to be the most effective method for both male and female students based on the mean gain. Male students generally performed better than female students across the two methods.

Research Question 3: What is the perception of year one undergraduate Mathematics students' towards Calculus when using Mathway application?

Table 3: Descriptive of responses of students' perceptions toward Calculus using Mathway application.

ITEM	Mean	SD	Remark
A. Mathway App for Teaching and Learning Calculus			
1. The Mathway App enhances my understanding of Calculus concepts.	3.18	0.46	positive
2. Mathway App provides clear explanation of Calculus problems.	3.25	0.53	positive
3. The Mathway App effectively supports self-paced learning of Calculus.	3.34	0.59	positive
4. The Mathway App interface is user friendly and easy to navigate.	3.34	0.57	positive
5. Mathway App provides helpful step-by-step solutions for Calculus problems.	3.35	0.60	positive
6. The use of Mathway App encourages active engagement with Calculus content.	3.03	0.61	positive
7. Mathway App features aligns with my Calculus learning goals.	3.06	0.85	positive
8. The Mathway adapts well to differentiate learning styles.	3.25	0.66	positive
9. Mathway App creates an opportunity for me to practices and learns more Calculus.	2.35	0.72	negative
10. The Mathway App fosters a deeper understanding of the pedagogical aspects of Calculus.	2.80	0.71	positive
11. Mathway enhances my problem-solving skills in Calculus.	3.03	0.64	positive
12. The Mathway App explanations are tailored to my level of Calculus knowledge.	3.18	0.50	positive
13. Mathway complements my classroom learning experience.	3.02	0.67	positive
14. Mathway encourages critical thinking in Calculus problem-solving.	3.06	0.61	positive
15. Calculus with Mathway promotes individual learning.	3.25	0.53	positive
Perception Sub-Scale Mean	3.14	0.62	positive
B. Mathway App for Collaborative Learning in Calculus			
16. Mathway App facilitates collaboration with classmates while learning Calculus.	3.00	0.35	positive
17. Collaborative learning with the Mathway App helps me understand Calculus concepts better.	2.91	0.70	Positive
18. Mathway allows me to easily share and discuss Calculus problems	3.02	0.72	Positive
19. Collaborating with others using Mathway App enhances my problem-solving skills in Calculus.	2.86	0.81	positive
20. Mathway App encourages productive discussions and teamwork among students.	2.95	0.82	Positive
21. Collaborative learning with Mathway has improved my overall performance in Calculus.	3.20	0.47	Positive
22. The use of Mathway promotes peer teaching and learning in Calculus.	2.18	0.82	negative

23. Collaborative activities with Mathway are integral part of my Calculus learning experience.	3.05	0.51	positive
24. Working with others on Calculus problems using the Mathway App is enjoyable.	3.05	0.86	Positive
25. My Calculus need are met by the use of Mathway App.	2.97	0.81	Positive
26. Using Mathway App fosters a sense of community among Calculus learners.	3.06	0.56	Positive
27. I have some sense of security in my Calculus skills when working with the Mathway App.	2.95	0.60	Positive
28. I believed that collaborative learning with Mathway prepares me for real-world problem-solving.	2.95	0.62	Positive
29. The Mathway App collaborative features are user-friendly and accessible.	3.00	0.85	Positive
30. Maple’s collaborative tools promote active engagement among students.	3.18	0.50	Positive
31. Mathway App enhances a high sense of accountability among students in group work.	3.06	0.50	Positive
32. I would recommend using Mathway App for collaborative learning in Calculus to others.	3.38	0.52	Positive
33. I will explore Mathway App in other strands of mathematics like Algebra and Statistics.	3.40	0.88	Positive
Perception Sub-Scale Mean	3.05	0.66	Positive
Grand Mean	3.10	0.64	Positive

Table 3: shows different subscales of perception towards Calculus using Mathway application. Referenced on table 3, the mean values of items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8,10, 11, 12, 13, 14 and 15 suggest a positive perception, while the mean value of items 9 indicates a negative perception for teaching and learning calculus using Mathway application. Similarly, items 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32 and 33 demonstrate a positive perception with values above the criterion mean of 2.5 as mean value of item 22 falls below the criterion mean which suggest a negative perception for the sub-scale of value towards collaborative learning in Calculus using Mathway application. However, considering the Grand mean of 3.10, it indicated a positive perception as 3.10 is above the criterion mean of 2.5. Therefore, there was a positive perception of year one undergraduate Mathematics students’ in learning Calculus using the Mathway application.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean performance scores of year one undergraduate Mathematics students’ taught Calculus using Mathway application and those taught using the Lecture method.

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA on the difference in the mean performance score of year one undergraduate Mathematics students taught Calculus using the Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method

Dependent Variable: Posttest						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	6919.552 ^a	2	3459.776	85.745	.000	.599
Intercept	12169.912	1	12169.912	301.611	.000	.724
Pretest	1660.948	1	1660.948	41.164	.000	.264
Group	4697.443	1	4697.443	116.418	.000	.503
Error	4640.219	115	40.350			
Total	484069.000	118				
Corrected Total	11559.771	117				

a R Squared = .599 (Adjusted R Squared = .592)

Table 5 above showed that there was a significant difference in the mean performance scores between year one undergraduate Mathematics students’ taught Calculus using Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method ($F_{1, 115} = 116.42, p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis one was rejected at 5% significance level. The partial Eta squared estimated the effect size of the dependent variable on the independent variables. The Partial Eta squared is 0.503, which according to Cohen proposal is a moderate or medium effect. This accounts for about 50.3%.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the post-test mean performance scores of male and female year one undergraduate Mathematics students who were taught Calculus using Mathway application.

Table 6: Independent sample t Test of the difference in the mean performance score of male and female year one undergraduate Mathematics students taught Calculus using the Mathway application

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Post-test for Mathway group	Equal variances assumed	.629	.431	.132	63	.896	.22358	1.69840	-3.17041	3.61757
	Equal variances not assumed			.128	44.448	.899	.22358	1.74413	-3.29048	3.73764

Results from table 6 indicates a not significant difference between male ($M = 69.39$, $SD = 6.36$) and female ($M = 69.17$, $SD = 7.03$), [$t(63) = 0.132$, $p = 0.896 > 0.05$]. The 95% confidence interval of the difference between means ranges from $[-3.17041$ to $3.73764]$ and did not indicate a difference between the means of the sample. Since the probability value of 0.896 is greater than the significance level of 0.05, we then accept the null hypothesis of There is no significant difference between the post-test mean performance scores of male and female year one undergraduate Mathematics students who were taught Calculus using Mathway application.

Discussion of Findings

The data in table 1 revealed that Students taught with Mathway were favoured more that those taught with the lecture method. Also, there was a significant difference in the mean performance scores between year one undergraduate Mathematics students’ taught Calculus using Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method. This result supports with that of Ghanem and Yahya (2022) with a statistical significant difference between students that used Mathway and those that did not use Mathway in learning Mathematics. It aligns with Hadjinor, Asotigue, and Pangandamun (2021) study with significant difference between pre-test and post-test performance of students that use Mathway application for solving trigonometric problems. The result is also similar to Onaifoh and Ekwueme (2017)

study who also found that there was a significant difference between the mean performances of students' taught plane geometry using GeoGebra software and problem-based learning but no significant difference was observed with respect to gender.

The data in table 2 revealed that male students using the Mathway application had a mean gain of 35.68, while female students had a mean gain of 34.84. Male students using the Lecture Method had the lowest mean gain of 24.36, while female students had a mean gain of 21.12. The Mathway application seemed to be the most effective method for both male and female students based on the mean gain. Male students generally performed better than female students across the two methods.

The data in table 3 revealed that undergraduate Mathematics students generally perceive the learning of calculus positively when using Mathway application. This finding collaborate with that of (Byiringiro,2024; Charles-Ogan & Gamage, 2019). The results unveiled that students had positive perception towards mathematics learning.

The data in table 5 revealed that there was a significant difference in the mean performance scores between year one undergraduate Mathematics students' taught Calculus using Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method ($F_{1, 115} = 116.42, p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis one was rejected at 5% significance level. This result is in line with that of Gbanem and Yahya, 2022.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that Students taught with Mathway were favoured more than those taught with the lecture method, likewise, there was a significant difference in the mean performance scores between year one undergraduate Mathematics students' taught Calculus using Mathway application and those taught using the lecture method. Male students slightly performed higher than their female counterparts using Mathway application. Also, there was no significant difference between male and female year one undergraduate Mathematics students' performance in Calculus using Mathway application. And finally, undergraduate Mathematics students' positively perceived the learning of Calculus when using Mathway application.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following among other things that:

1. The government should provide Mathway application across tertiary institutions in Bayelsa State to enhance lecturers' variation of teaching methods.
2. Lecturers should be trained on the use of Mathway to enable them teach with the application as computer assisted instructional facilities.

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